

18. Uluslararası Güncel Araştırmalarla Sosyal Bilimler Kongresi Tam Metinleri
Book of Proceeding The 18th International Congress on Social Studies with Recent Research
كتاب المتون الكاملة للمؤتمر الدولي الثامن عشر للدراسات الاجتماعية والتاريخية والقانونية

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ÖN SÖZ

18. Uluslararası Güncel Araştırmalarla Sosyal Bilimler Kongresi, 08-11 Ekim 2024 tarihlerinde Ankara'da gerçekleşecektir. Bu kongre, Saybilder Topluluğunun organizasyonunda ve başta Ankara Hacı Bayram Veli Üniversitesi, Mardin Artuklu Üniversitesi, Carthage University olmak üzere çeşitli yükseköğretim kurumlarının ilmi desteği ile düzenlenmektedir. Kongreye 6 farklı ülkeden davetli konuşmacı davet edilmiştir. Aynı zamanda Türkçe, İngilizce ve Arapça duyurular yapılarak bilim insanlarına çağrıda bulunulmuştur. Bu çağrılar sonrasında Türkiye hariç 12 farklı ülkeden (Birleşik Arap Emirlikleri, Cezayir, Fas, Irak, Katar, Kazakistan, Libya, Mısır, Suudi Arabistan Krallığı, Tunus, Umman, Ürdün) sözlü bildiri kongre programına dâhil edilmiştir. Tüm bildiriler kör hakemlik sürecinden geçirildikten sonra sunuma kabul veya reddi gerçekleştirilmiştir. Bu süreç içerisinde bildirilerin önemli bir kısmına hakemlerden düzeltme talebi gelmiştir. Hakemler tarafından talep edilen düzeltmelerin yapılıp yapılmadığı da özenle kontrol edilmiş ve düzeltilerden sonra kabul mektupları düzenlenerek yazarlarına gönderilmiştir.

Başvuru süreci sonucunda 73'ü Türk bilim insanları tarafından ve 77'si farklı ülkelerden katılan bilim insanları tarafından hazırlanmış toplam 150 bildiri sözlü sunuma uygun bulunmuştur. Bu kitapta kongrede sunulan bildirilere ait tam metinler yer almaktadır.

Kongrenin bilim insanları arasındaki iletişimi kuvvetlendirmesini, bilgi alışverişini arttırmasını, ortak çalışma zeminlerini oluşturmasını, milletimize, insanlığa ve bilgiyle amel edenlere faydalı olmasını diliyorum.

Prof. Dr. Hüseyin Akyüz
Düzenleme Kurulu Başkanı

مقدمة

يسرنا أن نقدم لكم هذا الكتاب الذي يضم مجموعة الأبحاث الكاملة التي قُدمت خلال فعاليات المؤتمر الدولي الثامن عشر للدراسات الاجتماعية والتاريخية والقانونية، الذي عُقد في العاصمة التركية أنقرة خلال الفترة من 8 إلى 11 أكتوبر. كان هذا المؤتمر فرصة مميزة لتبادل الأفكار والمعرفة بين نخبة من الباحثين والأكاديميين المتخصصين في مجالات الدراسات الاجتماعية والتاريخية والقانونية، حيث تميز بالتنوع الفكري والتخصصي الذي يعكس تطور هذه المجالات الحيوية.

شهد المؤتمر مشاركات واسعة من باحثين من مختلف الجامعات والمؤسسات العلمية حول العالم، وأسهم في مناقشة العديد من القضايا المحورية التي تتعلق بالتحديات الاجتماعية والقانونية التي تواجه المجتمعات المعاصرة. كما تناولت الأبحاث المقدمة مواضيع تتعلق بالتاريخ وارتباطه بتشكيل البنى الاجتماعية والقانونية في الحاضر، مما أضفى بعداً تحليلياً معمقاً على المناقشات العلمية.

إن هذا الكتاب يضم بين دفتيه نتاج جهود بحثية متميزة أسهمت في تقديم رؤى نقدية ومعرفية حول قضايا متشابكة ومعقدة، مع السعي إلى تقديم حلول مستدامة للتحديات القانونية والاجتماعية القائمة. ولعل هذا التنوع في الأبحاث يعكس مدى أهمية المؤتمر في تعزيز التفاهم العلمي وتوسيع آفاق الحوار الأكاديمي بين الباحثين في مختلف التخصصات. نتمنى أن يجد القارئ في هذا الكتاب إضافة قيمة إلى المعرفة العلمية، وأن يساهم في تطوير الدراسات الاجتماعية والتاريخية والقانونية بما يعزز التقدم الفكري والاجتماعي للمجتمعات.

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Recent Developments in Central Bank Digital Currency Projects: Quo Vadis?

Prof. Dr. Ali Polat

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Abstract

The emergence of Central Bank Digital Currencies (CBDCs) represents a pivotal evolution in the global financial architecture, with profound implications for monetary policy, financial stability, and the efficiency of payment systems. This paper seeks to provide a comprehensive analysis of recent developments in CBDC projects across various regions, focusing on the underlying motivations driving central banks towards digital currency adoption. It delves into the diverse design choices, such as account-based versus token-based systems, and the varying degrees of centralization in CBDC implementation. Through a comparative analysis of case studies from central banks in developed and emerging economies, the research identifies key trends, including the push for greater financial inclusion, the need for more resilient and efficient cross-border payment systems, and the potential for CBDCs to serve as tools for combating illicit financial activities.

The study also explores the emerging challenges associated with CBDC deployment, particularly in areas of cybersecurity, data privacy, and the potential disintermediation of the banking sector. The findings suggest that while CBDCs have the potential to revolutionize financial systems by providing faster, more secure transactions and enhancing central banks' control over monetary policy, they also introduce significant risks that must be carefully managed. These risks include potential cybersecurity threats, the erosion of privacy, and the challenge of ensuring interoperability across different CBDC systems. The paper concludes by discussing the future trajectory of CBDC adoption, emphasizing the importance of international collaboration in establishing regulatory frameworks and standards to mitigate these risks and maximize the benefits of CBDCs.

Keywords: Money, Payments, CBDC, Cross-Border Transactions

Introduction

The way people use money is changing alongside rapid advancements in payment technologies. The rise of the internet and digital networks has paved the way for peer-to-peer digital transactions, which have the potential to significantly change payment and financial intermediation systems. This technological shift, coupled with the need to manage money usage, presents new economic challenges, including the emergence of digital currencies, for agents such as central banks (Riani & Akbar, 2024).

Payment systems are the circulation mechanisms of modern monetary economies. Through these systems, it is possible to ensure that expenditures and savings are delivered to the correct person or institution, at the right time, and in the right place. The presence of stable payment systems is of critical importance not only for central bankers but also for policymakers. Discussions on payment systems in general, and cross-border payment systems in particular,

existed even before the debates surrounding Central Bank Digital Currency (CBDC), which is the focus of this study, emerged. The fact that payments in many economies generate costs equivalent to around 3% of total GDP has brought payment and settlement systems' development, management, and the application of innovations in this area into the realm of central banks, which are responsible for maintaining financial and monetary stability by managing legal, operational, security, and various economic risks related to payments (Fry et al., 2005). Historically, central banks and payment systems have been inseparably linked, but this historical relationship is being reshaped by technology (Haldane et al., 2008) and depending on the scope and effectiveness of global efforts by sovereign states, this link may weaken or even break.

Advancements in digitization, blockchain technology, smart contracts, artificial intelligence, and natural language processing all have direct or indirect effects on banking and payment systems. For this reason, organizations like the Bank for International Settlements (BIS) and the International Monetary Fund (IMF) are discussing the advantages and disadvantages of CBDC. As Baeriswly (2023) has noted, the decline in cash demand in certain jurisdictions has been a defining factor in the emergence of a different form of central bank money. The increasing dependence of economies on electronic payment systems has also led to the idea of establishing a type of backup system, which can be described as CBDC. Distributed Ledger Technologies (DLT) and other technologies accelerating digitization have contributed to the concentration within payment systems. From this perspective, it can be argued that CBDC could potentially contribute to the independence of national payment systems.

This study aims to examine the use of CBDC addressing its technical and political-economic dimensions, and discussing the potential opportunities and threats. Although the subject is relatively new, a rapidly growing body of literature on the topic is emerging. Central banks have various design preferences when it comes to issuing CBDCs, and each design choice comes with its own set of advantages and disadvantages (Auer & Böhme, 2020). Moreover, beyond technical limitations and requirements, there are other variables influencing a country's choice regarding CBDC. For example, different cultural values can affect the transition to CBDC (Luu et al., 2022). The study conducted by Luu et al. (2022) used Hofstede's cultural dimensions theory, which includes dimensions such as power distance, individualism, uncertainty avoidance, and masculinity. It was found that societies characterized by high power distance, masculinity, and long-term orientation were more eager to adapt to CBDC, while societies that tend to avoid uncertainty were less interested. Similarly, Maryaningsih et al. (2022) found that countries with advanced financial systems and significant cross-border transactions tend to prefer wholesale CBDCs, while countries with lower financial accessibility and larger informal economies opt for retail CBDCs. Although there are many other variables at play, the fundamental distinction in CBDC design lies in whether the system will be internal, used by individuals, or global, facilitating cross-border transactions. Therefore, the actions taken by central banks extend beyond purely technical considerations, encompassing cultural, sociological, and individual characteristics. For example, a survey conducted with 344 CBDC users in 10 pilot regions in China revealed that factors such as convenience, perceived security level, and perceived ease of use positively influenced CBDC adoption (Liu et al., 2022)

Not only individual countries but also global organizations have emphasized the importance of CBDC and cross-border payments. In October 2020, the G20 underscored the need for improving cross-border payments. This emphasis is not only related to high costs, low speeds, and limited access but also to issues such as incompatibility of data types, complex compliance

procedures related to regulations, limited transaction hours, mandatory technology platforms, long transaction chains, funding costs, and weak competition (BIS, 2021). As can be seen, a body of literature concerning CBDC has begun to emerge, and there is a growing need for serious discussions on meaningful solutions for Turkey and its cross-border partners.

This study comprises three additional sections following the introduction. The first section addresses topics in the literature related to cross-border CBDCs. The second section explores the definition, objectives, and characteristics of CBDC. The third section discusses global applications and expectations together with discussion on use of CBDC in international payments, the last section concludes the study.

Literature Review

CBDC and its use in domestic and cross-border payments represent a significant issue with the potential to cause a paradigm shift in the global financial architecture. Although research, development, and implementation of tests and applications are ongoing, and the relevant literature continues to evolve, this is an exciting area of research. While there are many questions regarding its use within domestic economies, cross-border usage becomes even more complex. Auer et al. (2022) discuss the motivations behind CBDC projects, the economic expectations, and what needs to be addressed in future research. For example, the digitalization and development of China's currency, the Renminbi (RMB), as a CBDC is driven by China's goal to benefit more from global trade and increase the international use of the e-RMB, positioning it as a rival to the U.S. dollar's hegemony (van der Linden & Łasak, 2023). Thus, preferences and policies vary from country to country.

Šapkauskienė and Prialgauskaitė (2023) explain that the CBDC-related literature is categorized into four main topics: motivation, design, demand, and the overall impact on the financial system and monetary sovereignty. Therefore, while some studies take a broad view of CBDC, others focus on supply-side issues of CBDC projects, demand-side micro and macro topics, or the risks and benefits posed by this transformation. For instance, Kochergin and Dostov (2020) examine CBDC from both retail and wholesale perspectives and suggest that different models and design options could influence monetary policy implementation and central banks' interest. Deng (2020), addressing the challenges faced in cross-border payments, discusses blockchain technology's relevance and the importance of its use in cross-border payment systems.

In addition to academic studies, reports and presentations from international institutions are available on this topic. World Bank reports highlight that cross-border payment systems are a priority on the G20's agenda, emphasizing the need for faster, cheaper, more transparent, and inclusive cross-border payment services. These reports also evaluate the international dimensions of CBDC projects, with particular emphasis on the macro-financial impacts of cross-border payments (World Bank Group, 2021).

Auer et al. (2021) discuss the concept of multi-CBDC (mCBDC), which refers to the interoperability of different CBDCs with various technological and infrastructure characteristics for cross-border use. They argue that to realize the potential benefits, a system involving central banks must be established. To avoid repeating past mistakes, they propose setting up a highly coordinated system under the supervision of central banks. Syarifuddin (2023), using the meta-SWOT analysis method, explains the strengths and weaknesses, as well as external and internal threats, for developing countries in making CBDC-related choices.

Hyeon-Joo(2022) provides a general assessment, stating that CBDC applications also concern property rights and that a consensus is required for application preferences.

Themistocleous et al. (2023) emphasize that while there are models proposed by the BIS related to cross-border payments, and although there are many reports on the subject, academic studies are limited. They also mention that standards and interfaces need to be established moving forward, and new regulations related to legal issues, legislation, policy challenges, and governance are required.

Van Roosebeke and Defina (Van Roosebeke & Defina, 2023), noting the limited literature on cross-border assessments, argue that policies should be established regarding both the interoperability of CBDCs and the use of domestically produced CBDCs by foreign residents and non-residents. These policies include details on issues such as Know Your Customer (KYC) principles, cross-border cooperation on KYC policies, and well-calibrated and integrated settlement systems.

Definition and Features of CBDC

CBDC, at its most basic level, "represents a central bank liability and is stored electronically (as a digital or electronic token), which can be used to make payments"(Engert & Fung, 2017). While this broad definition includes current deposit accounts that commercial banks hold at the central bank within the scope of CBDC, there are many different types of CBDCs. Primarily, the literature distinguishes CBDCs into two categories: wholesale and retail. Retail central bank money is used by individuals and businesses, while wholesale CBDC is utilized by financial intermediaries. There are also different definitions of CBDC, as follows:

1. A form of digital central bank money different from traditional reserve or settlement account balances(Ward & Rochemont, 2019).
2. A central bank liability that is digital, potentially interest-bearing, centrally issued, and accessible to the general public through an account-based system(Bitter, 2020).
3. CBDC is an electronic form of central bank money that is (i) more widely accessible than reserves, (ii) more functional than cash for retail transactions, and (iii) operates under a different operational structure compared to other forms of central bank money, potentially serving a different core purpose(Kiff et al., 2020).
4. CBDC represents a central bank liability stored electronically and can be used to make payments (Bordo & Levin, 2017; Engert & Fung, 2017).
5. A digital fiat currency issued by a central bank(Ozili, 2021)

While these definitions can be expanded further, they collectively indicate that although CBDCs carry the functions of cash, they differ in their characteristics as a central bank liability. As much as defining what CBDC is, it is also essential to clarify what CBDC is not. According to R3 (2021), a digital asset falling under the definition of CBDC:

- Cannot be mined by unknown third parties.
- Cannot be tied to real-world assets.
- Is not the payment itself, but a means of payment.
- Is an infrastructure and does not pose a threat to the liabilities of the financial system.

Several arguments have been made in favor of CBDC issuance. According to the Bank for International Settlements (BIS), these include: 1) Issuing CBDC due to the decline in cash usage, 2) Establishing a system that will increase the resilience of payments as a form of systemic insurance, and 3) Enhancing the diversity and sovereignty of payment systems (ECB & BIS, 2020).

For countries and their central banks, the emergence of blockchain-based new technologies and payment methods, which provide direct and indirect opportunities that may threaten public authority, has increased the interest in CBDC. Other benefits include seigniorage revenues, reducing transaction costs, increasing speed, reducing the informal economy and tax losses, lowering real interest rates, and accelerating economic growth.

Even without the application of a CBDC-like innovation, the current situation can still be considered problematic. This is primarily due to private sector-based applications, especially in countries like China and India, through digital wallets and applications. Digital currencies issued by private individuals and institutions (virtual currencies, cryptocurrencies) aim to gain control over a power that has historically been the monopoly of states. As a result, sovereign states worldwide are evaluating options to either ban these efforts or produce digital currencies themselves (Çatlı & Şimşek, 2021). However, a digital system is always open to risks such as cyberattacks and hacking (Demir & Odabaşı, 2021). Therefore, it is crucial to avoid rushing into a full transition to CBDC in order to prevent systemic payment risks and ensure the adaptation of existing users. The continued use of physical cash alongside CBDC would serve as insurance against security risks and provide a transitional period for individuals with lower financial literacy.

While the definitions of CBDC in the literature have been outlined, it is also possible to answer the question of the differences between wholesale and retail CBDCs through specific characteristics, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Differences Between Wholesale CBDC and Retail CBDC

	Retail CBDC	Wholesale CBDC
Target Audience	General public, individuals, businesses	Financial institutions, banks, and other organizations
Usage	Used for everyday transactions	Used for large-value, interbank transactions
Transaction Volume	High transaction volume with low individual transaction values	Low transaction volume with high values
Account Holders	Usable by individuals, businesses, and financial institutions	Limited to authorized financial institutions
Accessibility	Broad access through digital wallets for the general public	Restricted access, limited to authorized institutions
Settlement Speed	Near real-time settlement for retail transactions	Instant settlement for wholesale transactions
Privacy	Enhanced privacy measures for individual users	Reduced privacy due to transparency requirements
Monetary Policy	Provides central banks with more direct control over monetary policy	Can impact monetary policy through interactions with banks
System Integration	Integration with existing retail payment infrastructure	Integration with existing wholesale payment systems
Risk Management	Emphasizes fraud prevention and consumer protection	Focuses on systemic risk management and financial stability

Source:(Overgaag, 2022)

Depending on the design choices of a particular central bank, the features and characteristics of CBDCs may vary. Thus, while Table 1 provides a general Abstract of the differences between wholesale and retail CBDCs, it may not capture all the nuances of each implementation. Furthermore, this study has a limited scope, so it does not cover other design issues such as whether the CBDC will be account-based or token-based, whether the blockchain will be closed or open, or whether Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT) will be used.

Auer, Cornelli, and Frost (2021) conducted a probit regression analysis and found that the digital infrastructure of countries (mobile phone usage and broadband subscriptions), innovation capacity, institutional characteristics (government effectiveness and the informal economy), development and financial advancement, and the public sector's interest in CBDC are all key determinants, along with cross-border payments (the ratio of remittances to GDP and the level of trade openness).

Global CBDC Practices and Expectations

Cross-border and domestic CBDC applications have several available databases. According to the database prepared by the Atlantic Council Geoeconomics Center, as of October 2024, 134 countries have taken some action regarding CBDC projects. Among these, 3 are launched, 44 pilot, 20 development, 39 research, 21 inactive, 2 cancelled and 5 other projects are available (Atlantic Council, 2024). Another database is CBDC Tracker, which aims to guide analysts by tracking developments related to CBDCs in different countries over time (Mikhalev et al., 2021). According to the data from Atlantic Council (2024), the details of cross-border CBDC projects are presented in Table 2 below.

Table 2: Cross-border CBDC Projects and Details

Project	Start Date	Participants	Purpose
mBridge	September 2021	Thailand, China, Hong Kong, UAE	Wholesale CBDC
Dunbar Project	March 2022	Australia, Singapore, Malaysia, South Africa	Wholesale CBDC
Sela Project	June 2022	BIS, Hong Kong, Israel	Two-tier cybersecurity issues
Icebreaker Project	September 2022	Israel, Norway, BIS	Linking different retail CBDCs for cross-border use
Mariana Project	November 2022	France, Singapore, Switzerland, BIS	Cross-border Automated Market Maker (AMM) for FX transfers
Jura Project	December 2021	France, Switzerland	Wholesale CBDC via DLT platform for cross-border settlement
Onyx/Multiple wCBDC	July 2021	France, Singapore	Developed with Monetary Authority of Singapore, JP Morgan Onyx unit
Rosalind Project	June 2022	UK, BIS	Intermediated two-tier prototype for retail CBDCs
Aurum Project	March 2021	BIS, Hong Kong	Token issuance for wholesale and retail CBDCs
Helvetia Project	2020	Switzerland, BIS	Wholesale CBDC on digital asset platform

Jasper Project	2017	Canada, UK, Singapore	Exploring DLT for cross-border payments
Aber Project	2019	UAE, Saudi Arabia	Cross-border payments with decentralized ledger technology

Source: Atlantic Council(2024)

These projects are both complementary and competitive in nature. In the current political economy, where global power is shifting from the West to the East, the question of who will control the new system of international payments, and the West's share in this system, will influence regulations and operations related to political sanctions, anti-money laundering, and combating the financing of terrorism. Perhaps for this reason, countries are both collaborating and acting independently in building these projects to secure themselves monetarily and politically in the new global payment system.

Discussions about CBDCs also touch on regulatory issues. If these gaps are not filled, central banks may face legal, financial, and reputational risks. For example, many central bank laws do not allow for the general use of CBDCs. Another issue concerns monetary law, as each sovereign country has the power to issue its currency. The design of CBDCs also determines how the legal foundations will be established(Arauz, 2021; Bossu et al., 2020) suggests that countries with low importance in the payment chain should improve their regulations for potential CBDC usage, especially regarding other blockchain-based cryptocurrencies. Additionally, applications such as Facebook's Diem and Novi wallet could impact the money creation process in a country, which must also be analyzed carefully. Money held outside the banking channel in electronic wallets poses risks of reducing bank deposits, altering the structure of money supply and demand functions, and potentially leading to liquidity crises due to the flexibility of private money issuance(Palley, 2001).

Conclusion

This study demonstrates that certain groups of countries and some organizations at the global level have engaged in significant efforts regarding CBDC, with increasing interest in this topic over the last decade. On one hand, the subject is highly technical, involving only a small group of technicians and central bankers, while on the other hand, it encompasses financial and political domains. Countries that seek to impose their global policies also introduce regulations related to the payments system, which are intertwined with numerous international security and policy concerns, such as KYC (Know Your Customer), anti-money laundering (AML), countering the financing of terrorism (CFT), and sanctions. Thus, the management of global payments, system design, market participants, and the payment infrastructure have, in many respects, become matters of national security.

One of the most critical aspects on a systemic level is the process known as "de-dollarization," which has the potential to diminish or even end American hegemony. The sanctions imposed and the freezing of assets following Russia's invasion of Ukraine have revived efforts to seek alternatives to the dollar. Policymakers in excessively dollar-dependent systems have begun to pursue realistic alternatives, initiating research and development processes on designs capable of facilitating both retail and wholesale payments. Although domestic system designs are concerned with internal stakeholders, for countries to engage in cross-border transactions, at least two nations must reach an agreement on the rules, procedures, and processes related to the monetary transfer mechanism. Without infrastructure in which central banks agree on

legal, technical, operational, financial, and risk management perspectives, and where their systems are interconnected, the use of CBDCs in international transactions will not be possible.

This study highlights that the use of CBDC in cross-border payment systems is much more than a technical issue and emphasizes the need for more academic and practical research in this field. We discussed several joint projects led by BIS and other international organizations at the global level. To the best of our knowledge, our country has not been involved in any joint project with another country or group of countries regarding cross-border payments.

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Recent Academic Studies

Yeni Pazar Mh. Ali Okumuş Cad. Mevlana Sitesi A Blok – Çayeli / Rize

في رحاب جامعة أنقرة يلدرم بيازيد في العاصمة التركية اجتمع علماء وباحثون متخصصون من مختلف بلدان العالم وقدموا مشاركاتهم وبحوثهم ضمن المؤتمر الدولي الثامن عشر للدراسات الاجتماعية والتاريخية والقانونية، يضم هذا الكتاب المتون الكاملة للأبحاث المقدمة، والتي نرجو أن تكون ذات فائدة للباحثين وذات أثر ايجابي علي المجتمع الأكاديمي وعلي المجتمع الإنساني ككل.